

PREP4BLUE

METHODS AND TOOLS FOR MISSION OCEAN & WATERS

Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters

Deliverable 6.3

Report on the findings of the stakeholder assembly's engagement pilots

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Executive Summary

PREP4BLUE, the first Coordination and Support Action (CSA) for the Mission Ocean and Waters, plays a critical role in supporting the Mission's objective of establishing a revamped governance model for oceans, seas, and waters, as well as enhancing public mobilization.

This report is one of the outcomes of the Work Package 6 activities on stakeholder engagement, which implements a multidisciplinary, multi-stakeholder approach based on the 'Penta-Helix Model.' This model includes industry, public authorities, academia, civil society, and environmental organizations, all working together to boost stakeholder engagement in the Mission.

The stakeholder engagement process of pilot assemblies within PREP4BLUE is built on a structured, multi-step approach: needs assessments, pre-engagement planning, and collaboration with LightHouse (LH) CSA projects.

PREP4BLUE's primary contribution has been the creation of comprehensive stakeholder engagement guidelines and toolkits, along with the *WaveLinks* platform for identifying and analysing stakeholder engagement methods.

These tools were tested through four regional pilot assemblies, held across different basins: Atlantic-Arctic, Mediterranean, Danube-Black Sea, and Baltic-North Sea. Each assembly focused on one of the Mission's key objectives, such as ecosystem restoration, pollution reduction, and fostering a sustainable blue economy. These assemblies brought together diverse stakeholders, fostering collaborative governance models, democratic participatory processes, and generating key outcomes, such as sub-regional roadmaps. The co-creation process was central to these assemblies, where participants from various sectors worked together to identify problems, discuss challenges, and create tangible solutions.

The pilot assemblies provided a tangible framework for stakeholder engagement, testing and validating relevant engagement methods and event formats that will guide future engagement strategies within the Mission Ocean and Waters.

This report delivers the main results of the pilot stakeholder assemblies, outlining the methodology and engagement process followed in each pilot. It also provides an analysis of the key methods tested, such as the World Café and the role-playing game, as well as relevant public consultation processes showcased during these events.

The main findings from the pilot assemblies, including methodologies, lessons learned, and best practices, will inform the design and implementation of future stakeholder engagements across the Mission Ocean and Waters. By testing and refining innovative engagement strategies, PREP4BLUE is paving the way for more effective governance and enhanced citizen and stakeholder involvement in ocean and water management, ultimately contributing to the achievement of the Mission's ambitious objectives.

Acronyms & Abbreviations

Table 1. Table of abbreviations and acronyms used in Prep4Blue and the document

Acronym / Abbreviation	Signification
BANOS	Baltic and North Sea
BMAA	BlueMissionAA – Blue Mission Atlantic and Arctic
BMBANOS	BlueMissionBanos – Blue Mission Baltic and North Sea
BMM	BlueMissionMed – Blue Mission Mediterranean
CSA(s)	Coordination and Support Action project(s)
CSOs	Civil Society Organisations
D6.1	Stakeholder engagement guidelines, including toolkit
D6.2	Stakeholder engagement recommendations
EcoDaLLi	ECOsysteM-based governance with DANube lighthouse Living Lab for sustainable Innovation processes
LH(s)	LightHouse(s)
MPA(s)	Marine Protected Area(s)
(the) Mission	Mission ‘Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030’ / Mission Ocean and Waters
NGO(s)	Non-Governmental Organization(s)
P4B	PREP4BLUE
SHEM	Stakeholder Engagement Methods

1 Setting the scene

1.1 Mission Ocean and Waters & the project PREP4BLUE

The Horizon Europe Programme for 2021-2027 is articulated around five missions, targeting the main challenges where research and innovation efforts should be concentrated. The Mission Ocean and Waters (hereafter also referred as The Mission) aims to restore our oceans, seas and waters by 2030, through the achievement of three main objectives:

- 1) Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity
- 2) Prevent and eliminate pollution
- 3) Make the sustainable blue economy carbon neutral and circular

Mission Ocean and Waters implements a change of paradigm in the scientific approach, as it goes beyond research and innovation to create new forms of governance and ways to connect with the citizens. Research and innovation solutions should be co-created and co-implemented, as fostering engagement at national, regional and local levels is key to producing optimal and tailor-made innovative solutions. The Mission supports regional engagement and cooperation through area-based “Lighthouses” in major sea/river basins: Atlantic-Arctic, Mediterranean Sea, Baltic-North Sea, and Danube-Black Sea. The aim of the Lighthouses is to develop, pilot, replicate and upscale innovative solutions, through Coordination and Support Action projects (CSAs).

The implementation of the Mission is supported by transversal actions or “cross-cutting enablers” that will provide access to a digital ocean and water knowledge system (digital twin of the ocean¹) and guarantee broad public mobilisation and engagement. This last aspect is at the heart of the Mission, to fill the emotional gap with our aquatic environment by envisioning that “every European citizen becomes a citizen of our ocean and waters”.²

PREP4BLUE is the first CSA project of the Mission Ocean & Waters, with the overarching objective to facilitate a successful implementation of the first phase of the Mission (2022-2025) by developing the co-creation and co-implementation of R&I modalities required to achieve the Mission objectives, and preparing the ground for inspiring and engaging citizens and stakeholders. The pilot stakeholder assemblies form an important component of PREP4BLUE’s activities on stakeholder engagement and provide a concrete approach to the rationale of the Mission to connect all segments of our society, for a better understanding of the value of our ocean and waters.

¹ <https://digitaltwinocan.mercator-ocean.eu/>

² Mission Starfish 2030: Restore our Ocean and Waters. Report of the Mission Board Healthy Oceans, Seas, Coastal and Inland Waters. European Commission Directorate-General for Research and Innovation. 2020

1.2 Context and overview of PREP4BLUE's stakeholder engagement activities

Enshrined in Mission's enabler on public mobilization and engagement, PREP4BLUE Work Package 6 (WP6) entitled "Stakeholder Engagement: Strategy, Connectivity and Capacity Building" aims to develop a multidisciplinary, multistakeholder approach based on the 'Penta-Helix Model' which includes industry/businesses, public authorities, citizens/local residents, academia/the knowledge sector and associations, and builds upon a culture of collaboration and recognition of the environment as fundamental in contributing to social innovation. The activities and results of this WP offer a wide range of tested recommendations and methods, as well as a help desk, accessible to all actors of the Mission, to ensure that the Mission's spirit of a revamped water governance model and strong emotional connection of all EU citizens with water ecosystems is well implemented in the projects of the Mission and serve as inspiration for other sea and waters related projects and initiatives.

The first phase of the implementation of WP6 consisted of producing a comprehensive **Stakeholder Engagement Guidelines including Toolkit** (D6.1)³, analysing how to best identify, map and approach stakeholders oriented toward the objectives of the Mission. These guidelines were leveraged in deliverable 6.2, providing a **set of recommendations for future key Mission R&I core activities, completed by a stakeholder engagement strategy**⁴. This second report therefore provides a structured and tested framework for stakeholder engagement, with insights and methodologies that can be adapted to various project contexts.

Additionally, a digital tool was developed for identifying and analysing projects related to stakeholder engagement methods, integrated into the [Wavelinks platform](#) (a total of 49 methods and their applications were identified and analysed from 161 deliverables in 65 significant projects). These results were fine-tuned during a collaborative workshop gathering stakeholder engagement experts and coordinator of Mission-related projects.⁵

Testing and implementing these methods and recommendations was thus part of the second phase of the work package implementation, through the so-called pilot stakeholder assemblies, implemented in Task 6.3. Uptake is also pursued through capacity building activities and a [help desk](#), designed to assist stakeholders involved in the MO Lighthouses in identifying and using resources catalogued and generated by the project, as well as specific training activities (T6.4 and T6.5).

1.3 Main objectives of the pilot stakeholder assemblies

Built as a support action to the CSAs in testing multi-stakeholder participatory governance models, the pilot stakeholder assemblies (Prep4Blue Task 6.3) worked as collaborative processes to offer a concrete implementation of the methods and recommendations analysed in the first phase of Stakeholder engagement. The assemblies therefore supported the transfer of the main results of the PREP4BLUE project and prepared the ground for stakeholders' participation in the projects of the Mission. The assemblies can thus serve as a validated model of stakeholder engagement to be further used in the Mission lighthouses.

³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10944584>

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10944557>

⁵ <https://prep4blue.eu/events/stakeholders2codesign-towards-impactful-stakeholder-engagement-in-the-mission-ocean-seas-and-waters/>

These pilot stakeholder assemblies are result-oriented gatherings, organised in person and focused on the specific Mission objective assigned to each Lighthouse.

Four pilot stakeholder assemblies were held, one for each lighthouse, tackling one of the Mission's objectives:

- **Atlantic and Arctic Pilot Stakeholder Assembly** → Protect and restore marine ecosystems and biodiversity
- **Mediterranean Pilot Stakeholder Assembly** → Prevent and eliminate pollution of our ocean, seas and water
- **Danube and Black Sea Pilot Stakeholder Assembly** → Protection and restore freshwater and marine ecosystems and biodiversity
- **Baltic and North Sea Pilot Stakeholder Assembly** → Make the sustainable blue economy carbon-neutral and circular

The Assemblies gathered actors from the quintuple or penta-helix model, which represents groups of stakeholders from Industry, Government, Academia, Civil Society and include also the environment as an important component of the discussion for knowledge production and innovation processes.

Figure 1: Groups of stakeholders described by the penta-helix model

Each stakeholder assembly was organized around a specific problem or question, offering concrete actions and solutions to address it. The co-creation and co-production process among quintuple helix stakeholders facilitated this reflection, leading to tangible outcomes. For instance, the result of the first Mission Arena of the BANOS lighthouse was the development of a regional roadmap for the Mission.

By showcasing the main findings of the stakeholder assembly' pilot, this report pursues the following objectives:

- Present an overview of each stakeholder assembly and their main findings
- Serve as a guiding tool for future Lighthouses' stakeholder assemblies
- Provide feedback on the engagement methodologies tested to validate and/or enhance them

2 Pilot stakeholder assemblies' methodology

The stakeholder assemblies were prepared based on the recommendations from Deliverables 6.1 and 6.2, as well as those from the PREP4BLUE Toolbox for citizen engagement.⁶ The [WaveLinks](#) tool for stakeholder engagement methods was a key support to guide the reflection on the format of these events and the methodologies to be tested.

The pre-engagement planning phase drew from these recommendations, with strong collaboration between PREP4BLUE and the CSAs. This collaboration focused on analysing the stakeholder needs of each lighthouse and agreeing on the main theme and engagement methods to be tested. Additionally, it ensured alignment with the work plans of each CSA, including events, key deliverables, and other relevant activities.

Nevertheless, before setting up the assemblies, the project clarified the distinction between the concept of 'citizens' and 'stakeholders', particularly to further distinguish the activities carried out in Work Package 3, focused on citizen engagement, and those from Work Package 6, focused on stakeholder engagement. Despite a remaining overlap and complementarities between these two work packages, this needed clarification was an essential step and can be considered as the first phase in the implementation of the stakeholder assemblies.

2.1 STEP 1- Stakeholders and citizens approaches

PREP4BLUE project provides the baseline for a smooth implementation of the first phase of the Mission Ocean and Waters and intends to reflect on and test impactful methods of social innovation, to boost citizen and stakeholder engagement. Therefore, Prep4Blue considers citizens and stakeholders as two different concepts. Within PREP4BLUE, '**citizens**' are defined as those sought to be engaged as individuals, while '**stakeholders**' are those sought to be engaged as representatives of organisations or interest groups. Citizen co-design and implementation takes place in activities that seek engagement with individuals as individuals, instead of representatives of organisations or groups.

However, some level of fluidity between the terms 'citizen' and 'stakeholder' must remain, as all stakeholders are, in fact, also citizens. Consequently, while engagement methods are not identical, they often share similarities or overlap. In some cases, both groups are engaged together in a single process (such as community participatory planning). The European Commission itself frequently uses the 'citizen/stakeholder' label in Mission Ocean and Waters funding calls, including the one that PREP4BLUE responded to.

Additionally, in PREP4BLUE WP6, when collecting and analysing Stakeholder Engagement Methods— and considering the relevant target stakeholder groups—the practice of grouping Citizens and Civil Society Organisations (CSOs) into a single category has been frequently replicated. This is evident in [Deliverable 6.2](#) and the [Wavelinks](#) tool. This approach stems from the fact that the data and information collected are aggregated, preventing the distinction made in PREP4BLUE from being fully applied.

⁶ <https://prep4blue.eu/results/>

2.2 STEP 2 - Lighthouse Needs Assessment

To support each Coordination and Support Action (CSA) and address the specific needs of stakeholders within each lighthouse, the project conducted a needs assessment to establish a baseline for the stakeholder assemblies.

The needs assessment commenced with interviews, initially conducted during the Mission Ocean & Waters Forum in Brussels in 2023, followed by a series of online meetings.

A questionnaire matrix, specifically based on [WP6 stakeholder engagement guidelines and toolkit](#), was sent to the LH CSA coordinators and work package leaders.⁷

The main objectives of the matrix were to:

- Agreeing on the main topic of the assembly and identify a specific date and place, since these events were held in person.
- Identifying the specific needs of each lighthouse in terms of stakeholder engagement, including stakeholder categories, interests, level of engagement, and collaborative governance models.
- Clarifying the potential outcomes from the co-creation and co-development process for each pilot stakeholder assembly.
- Fine-tune the selection of appropriate stakeholder engagement methods for each pilot assembly, particularly when using the [WaveLinks](#) online tool.

This was complemented by regular meetings with the CSAs, especially with those in the Atlantic, Mediterranean, and Danube/Black Sea regions.

2.3 STEP 3 - Stakeholder Assemblies Preparation Phase

The outcomes of the needs assessment phase were compiled in a detailed concept note for each assembly which was shared among PREP4BLUE partners and LH CSAs coordinators.

The concept note notably facilitated the elaboration of:

- A **draft agenda** for each assembly
- A **stakeholder list** - To facilitate communication about the event (*e.g.*, save the date, reminders, registration forms, and working documents).
- **Working documents and papers** (*e.g.* World Café Information Package, Role-playing game scenarios and characters description)

2.4 STEP 4 – Execution and Next Steps

The execution of the event program proceeded smoothly, with slight adjustments made to accommodate participants' needs and maintain high levels of engagement throughout. The stakeholder assemblies, in particular, fostered networking and created new opportunities both within and outside the Mission framework.

After the event, key outcomes and relevant documentation were shared with attendees and made publicly available on the PREP4BLUE and CPMR websites, ensuring that the results of the stakeholder assemblies were effectively followed up.

⁷ Annex 7.1

3 Outcomes of the pilot stakeholder assemblies

3.1 Baltic and North Sea lighthouse

The Baltic and North Sea pilot stakeholder assembly was fully integrated in the [first Mission Arena](#) organised in the framework of the CSA project BlueMissionBANOS. Focused on the geographical area encompassing Germany (Western Baltic), Denmark (North-East), Sweden (West/South) and Norway (South), it gathered a wide range of stakeholders that contributed together to the identification of key priorities for a carbon-neutral and circular blue economy in the Western Baltic sub-region.

Date: Nov 14-16, 2023

Place: Gothenburg, Sweden

Number of participants: 200

Scale: Sub-regional - Western Baltic (encompassing Germany (Western Baltic), Denmark (North-East), Sweden (West/South) and Norway (South) | Large gathering: More than 200 participants

Objective: Co-creation of a roadmap for the effective deployment of the Mission Ocean & Waters in this sub-region ([Roadmap 2030: Steps for the Effective Deployment of the Mission Ocean & Waters in the Western Baltic](#))

Stakeholders: Stakeholders covering all quintuple helix' groups were represented

Stakeholder engagement method tested: World Café

Pre-engagement phase:

- The preparatory process started a year ahead of the Mission Arena to guarantee the success of this big scale event. These three days major event necessitated months of preparation.
- The stakeholder mapping represented an important part of the pre-engagement phase. The Mission Ocean & Waters Charter and R&I projects acted as a gateway to get access to a wide range of potential participants and speakers to the event. Organisers also used the snowball method to finetune their stakeholder mapping. Targeting ocean literacy and diverse citizen engagement activities facilitated the identification of citizens, future participants to the Mission Arena.
- Workshop coordinators and rapporteurs of the different sessions were selected and engaged well in advance in the preparation process of the arena.
- Pre-identification of action points to structure the roadmap, which were shared to the registered participants ahead of the meeting.
- The registration tool facilitated the pre-engagement of participants and anticipated the elaboration of the roadmap. Preparatory meetings helped to fine-tune the content of the sessions, and the innovative solutions to be presented.

Outcomes:

37 workshops and pitching sessions were organised to co-create the roadmap with all the participants. Each workshop addressed one of the following themes, which each representing one of the main goals and actions of the 2030 roadmap: Blue food, bioresources, biotechnology; Low-trophic Aquaculture & Products; Ocean and coastal plans in the Region; Multi-use solutions, renewable energy, citizen engagement. It also tackled potential challenges and opportunities regarding technical solutions and innovation gaps, finance and funding, business engagement, and regulatory enablers and barriers.

The workshop discussions served to nurture roadmap priorities, which were voted on during the final plenary of the Arena. This co-decision process led to the validation of the [Roadmap 2030: Steps for the Effective Deployment of the Mission Ocean & Waters in the Western Baltic](#).

Post-event phase:

- Transfer of the roadmap among key actors (policy makers, project managers, etc.)
- Make the best use of the roadmap as a tool to significantly influence future political and industry initiatives and funding programmes at national, Baltic and EU levels.

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- Transfer of the roadmap among key actors (policy makers, project managers, etc.)
- Make the best use of the roadmap as a tool to significantly influence future political and industry initiatives and funding programmes, at national, Baltic and EU levels.

Figure 2: Plenary session of the 1st Mission Arena BANOS

Figure 3: Visual of the Roadmap 2030 adopted during the 1st Mission Arena BANOS

3.2 Atlantic and Arctic lighthouse

In the Atlantic and Arctic lighthouse, the pilot stakeholder assembly focused on the first objective of the Mission Ocean and Waters: *Restoring and preserving marine ecosystems and biodiversity*. This focus, as identified in the needs assessment, targeted Atlantic stakeholders. In the Atlantic region, initiatives such as restoration measures and the expansion of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) can pose challenges in collaborating with and engaging diverse stakeholder groups, particularly those most affected. To address this, the assembly, hosted by the region of Nouvelle-Aquitaine and in collaboration with the CSA BlueMissionAA and the Atlantic innovation actions projects, showcased innovative consultation processes.

The approach was based on a game format to help people deal with challenging decisions or conflicts. It encourages empathy, improves decision-making, and gets people more involved. This method uses the serious game method to simulate real-world scenarios, allowing participants to practice conflict resolution and collaborative problem-solving in a safe setting. By engaging in these interactive simulations, stakeholders can better understand different viewpoints learn how to communicate and cooperate more effectively.

Date: 20 November 2024

Place: Bordeaux, France

Number of participants: 20

Scale: Regional: Atlantic Arc – Small-scale: Small group of participants

Objective:

- Showcase innovative national and regional consultation processes: The regional model of ‘sea parliaments’ and an unprecedented large-scale public consultation exercise conducted in France ‘[the sea in debate](#)’.
- Test an experimental role-playing game based on two scenarios inspired by the [CLIMAREST](#) and [OCEAN CITIZEN](#) projects. The game used fictive characters from the quintuple helix model to identify solutions applicable in real-life situations. [Synergie Littoral](#), a startup specializing in mediation and stakeholder dialogue provided support as moderator to implement this innovative game.
- The event was held alongside the annual [Atlantic Stakeholder Platform Conference](#) and contributed the discussions within the [Atlantic Strategy Pillar IV](#), focusing on a healthy ocean and resilient coasts.

Categories of stakeholders: Atlantic LH Project Managers, policymakers, researchers, and civil society organizations (CSOs)

Stakeholder engagement method tested: Role-playing game based on fictive scenarios

Pre-engagement phase:

- Stakeholder needs assessment and mapping: The CSA project [BlueMissionAA](#) served as a gateway to get access to a wide community of stakeholders in the Atlantic region. PREP4BLUE therefore strongly collaborated with the project partners to conduct the stakeholder needs assessment and mapping.
- Preliminary engagement with the Atlantic LH community: PREP4BLUE and [BlueMissionAA](#) collaboration officially kicked off with PREP4BLUE’s participation in the [Ocean Best Practice focus session](#), held online on the October 20th, 2023. This session showcased best practices of stakeholder engagement in ecosystem restoration, which supported the identification of key challenges to be addressed in the Atlantic and Artic stakeholder assembly.
- Questionnaire and interviews with innovation project managers of the Atlantic and Artic LH: The role-playing game required the development of two distinct scenarios based on real case studies. To create these scenarios, a series of interviews were conducted with innovation project coordinators, specifically from [CLIMAREST](#) and [OCEAN CITIZEN](#). These interviews helped identifying relevant case studies to build upon for the fictional scenarios, as well as experts to participate in the Atlantic and Artic stakeholder assembly and provide guidance throughout the discussions.
- Selection of a service provider to support the moderation of the role-playing game
- Elaboration of the role-playing game scenarios and fictive characters in collaboration with the professional moderator ([Synergie Littoral](#)).

Outcomes:

- o Atlantic stakeholders informed about innovative consultation processes, on which they can participate, in particular the regional sea parliaments.⁸
- o The role-playing game appeared as an excellent simulation tool for stakeholder pre-engagement. It can be notably used in the Atlantic region in the case of a restoration project and the implementation of an MPA. It also provided inspiration for a potential expansion of its use for maritime spatial planning and conflicts of use.

Post-event phase:

- o Dissemination of the game’s guidelines. Potential capitalization activity to further showcase the regional ‘sea parliament’ model and enhance cooperation opportunities

Figure 4: Group photo of the AA Pilot Stakeholder Assembly

Figure 5: Group playing the MPA scenario

⁸ Pays de la Loire Region '[assemblée régionale mer et littoral](#)'. Occitanie Region '[Le Parlement de la Mer](#)'

Figure 6: Group playing the oyster restoration scenario

3.3 Mediterranean lighthouse

Through the Mediterranean pilot stakeholder assembly, the CNR could connect the activities in PREP4BLUE and [BlueMissionMed](#) by offering a wider perspective to the Mediterranean lighthouse in addressing the issue of eliminating pollution from our ocean, seas and rivers. This one-day in-person event, offered a forum to present good practices of river and water management implemented by various cities and regions in Italy, and start a cross-fertilization process between these initiatives and the Mission Ocean and Waters lighthouses, amplifying the impact from the local and national level, to the Mediterranean and beyond.

Date: 21 May 2024

Number of participants: 140

Place: Rome, Italy

Scale: National and Mediterranean (focus on Italian initiatives, with the participation of representatives from different EU sea-basins).

Objective: Address the issue of river and water management in the Mediterranean LH by bridging local and European initiatives, to scale-up their impact in the Mediterranean and in all the Mission lighthouses.

Stakeholders: Local and regional authorities, representatives of National Ministries, associations of category, NGOs, students, educators, researchers, and SMEs

Stakeholder engagement method tested: Networking

Pre-engagement phase:

- The community of actors created throughout the LH CSA project BlueMissionMed facilitated the invitation of participants and speakers. CNR notably mobilized its network and the network of other partners organisations.

- The need to address this specific issue notably emerged from the activities of the project BlueMissionMed, and facilitated the preparation of the event, in collaboration with PREP4BLUE.

Outcomes:

- Landing of the Mission Ocean and Waters at the local level, by introducing it to a diverse audience including representatives from Italian local and regional authorities, national ministries, NGOs, students and researchers of Italian schools and universities
- Showcasing of the River Contracts model implemented in Italy, for a potential scaling up at the Mediterranean and European level
- Presentation of citizen science initiatives, highlighting the role of local communities in river health
- Increased knowledge on cases studies of freshwater biodiversity protection and river restoration from international projects across the Danube, Thames, Rio de Aveiro, and Po rivers.
- Boost collaboration opportunities for improved river-system management and innovative river restoration models.

Post-event phase:

- Information diffusion at the Mission Ocean and Waters level

Figure 7: Advertising of the Mediterranean pilot stakeholder assembly event

Figure 8: Picture of the Mediterranean Pilot Stakeholder Assembly

3.4 Danube and Black Sea lighthouse

Kindly hosted by Batumi Maritime State Academy, in Ajara Autonomous Republic, the Danube and Black Sea pilot stakeholder assembly fostered the engagement of Black Sea stakeholders in the Mission Ocean and Waters, and cross-fertilization opportunities between Danube and Black Sea initiatives for the conservation of marine and freshwater ecosystems. The event was notably co-organised with the CSA project [EcoDaLLi](#). Through a co-creation exercise to elaborate a strategic roadmap, the attendees identified the main priorities in the Danube and the Black Sea regarding nature-based solutions, innovation ecosystems, water systems and climate change.

Date: November 5-7, 2024

Number of participants: 40

Scale: Cross-basin: Danube and Black Sea / Meeting of medium scale

Objective: Connect stakeholders from the Black Sea with the Danube and with the Mission Ocean and Waters community & co-create an action plan to be incorporated in the EcoDaLLi roadmap.⁹

Categories of stakeholders: Representatives from State Administration, Local and Regional Authorities, Chambers of Commerce, business, academia, research centres and institutes, students and young scientists, civil society organisations, and the European Commission

Stakeholder engagement method tested: World Café

⁹ The Black Sea draft action plan is available in *Annex 7.2*. This is a separate section of the EcoDaLLi draft roadmap for the effective achievement of the Mission Ocean & Waters objectives in the Danube and Black Sea Lighthouse.

Pre-engagement phase:

- The launching event of the Danube and Black Sea lighthouse in Bucharest, Romania, in April 3-4 2023, fostered the connection with the [EcoDaLLi](#) project team and served to assess their main needs. In particular, the Black Sea basin was added to the Danube lighthouse after the launch of the Mission Ocean and Waters and the project EcoDaLLi which just started the elaboration of the project's living labs. Boosting this connection between the Black Sea and the Danube basins appeared as the main need for this lighthouse and thus the objective pursued by the pilot stakeholder assembly.
- Through the questionnaire matrix and a series of interviews with EcoDaLLi project coordinator and partners, PREP4BLUE could fine-tune the full programme of the event, elaborate the World Café topics and working documents, and thus the main architecture of the roadmap and action plan.
- Stakeholder mapping: PREP4BLUE benefited from EcoDaLLi's network to elaborate a list of stakeholders, which was completed by CPMR Balkan and Black Sea Commission's network.
- This comprehensive list of stakeholders served as a strong basis for stakeholders' pre-engagement in the pilot assembly. It notably facilitated email sendings, potential contacts with pre-registered participants and selection of rapporteurs for each round table.

Outcomes:

- Co-creation of an action plan identifying key priorities to boost innovation and research for the conservation of marine ecosystems and biodiversity in the Black Sea basin and cross-fertilization opportunities with initiatives in the Danube. Participants notably elaborated a set of key recommendations addressing main challenges and opportunities regarding nature-based solutions, innovation ecosystems, water systems, climate change, biodiversity and cross-border cooperation.
- The event boosted networking opportunities between Black Sea and Danube stakeholders.

Post-event phase:

- Analysis of the results from the World-Café sessions and follow-up discussions with Black Sea stakeholders to: rank the results, get some additional inputs, and fine-tune a draft specific Action Plan for the Black Sea region .
- Diffusion of the draft roadmap and action plan to the Danube and Black Lighthouse
- Maximise network and lighthouse activities implementation based on the outcomes of the pilot assembly

Figure 9: Group photo at the Danube and Black Sea Pilot Stakeholder Assembly

4 Analysis of the stakeholder engagement methods tested

The pilot stakeholder assemblies enabled the testing of different stakeholder engagement methods in the Mission Ocean and Waters lighthouses. Although these methods were selected based on the needs and context of a specific sea-basin and oriented towards a Mission objective, they can be applicable in different geographical areas and contribute to the achievement of several Mission objectives and cross-cutting enablers.

Throughout the implementation of PREP4BLUE stakeholder assemblies, a few methods appeared as particularly effective and fit with the social innovation spirit of Mission Ocean and Waters. As a result, this part concentrates on the world café, role-playing game and public consultation processes used during the stakeholder assemblies.

This feedback will notably enrich the description of the engagement methods available on WaveLinks.

4.1 Focus on World Café

The World Café method was considered by PREP4BLUE project as one of the best suited stakeholder engagement methods for results-oriented stakeholder gatherings. This method was used both in BANOS and Danube & Black Sea pilot stakeholder assemblies.

What is a World Café?

A World Café consists of bringing together a group of people around topics of common interest to strengthen their connections and commitment. It is also a way of accessing collective intelligence and creating innovative possibilities for action. In general, this technique represents a brainstorming tool that is less formal than a simple meeting and takes advantage of a small group to more easily engage everyone's participation.¹⁰

It notably facilitates meaningful conversations, gathers diverse perspectives, generates a wide range of ideas and solutions.

Why using the World Café method?

When stakeholder assemblies have the ambition to elaborate a specific policy, World Café can strongly support a co-creation process with a tangible result, in a democratic way.

Fit for stakeholders! As described above, stakeholders are mainly specialists with a thorough understanding of their area of expertise. The discussions taking place in the round tables help to extract this technical knowledge from the participants to elaborate a policy that reflects the needs on the ground and is based on the best available science.

Is it Democratic? The democratic aspect of an event based on a World Café lies in its collaborative nature. All attendees can participate in the debate and therefore in the elaboration of the tangible result of the assembly (such as for example a policy document).¹¹ Nevertheless, the World Café tested by PREP4BLUE can be considered as a representative democracy, since a rapporteur was designated in each table or session to represent the group during the plenary session and extract the main

¹⁰ World Café definition from WaveLinks platform. <https://wavelinks.eu/explore/engagement-methods/332>

¹¹ For example, the first [Mission Arena roadmap 2030](#).

relevant outcomes of the discussion to facilitate the roadmap elaboration. In this case, the final vote through an interactive tool like [Slido](#) offered a direct democratic decision-making method.

Fit for large-scale and smaller-scale event: World Café method is applicable to large-scale and smaller-scale events. This method was implemented in the first Mission Arena of BlueMissionBANOS and continues to be the main format of the Mission arenas. These large-scale events gather each year more than 200 participants. This method was also used during the pilot assembly organised in Georgia, with around 40 participants. If well prepared and designed in advance, the World Café method can turn a large-scale event into a very dynamic and participatory stakeholder gathering. Each attendee can make their voice heard and learn more about other initiatives. It transforms a standard event into a much more interactive moment.

Methodology

Clearly identify the result to be achieved by the World Café and the topics to be discussed. Identifying well in advance where the assembly should lead the participants is essential when organizing a World Café. Based on this objective the organisers can identify the main topics that will be discussed in each table. This step forms the backbone of the World Café.

Structure the discussions and pre-engage stakeholders. Sparking a debate among a group of stakeholders that do not know each other and work in very different areas is not an easy task. Pre-structuring the debate will boost the participation and put all the stakeholders in a comfortable zone to share their inputs. Providing working documents and a first set of key questions to be tackled during the World Café will help participants to understand what is required from them so they can directly enter the conversation. For example, a World Café information package was sent to the registered participants a week ahead of the Danube and Black Sea stakeholder assembly. This information package contained background information on each topic of the world café, with a set of questions to prepare the debates.

The role of moderator and rapporteur is key. Selecting moderators and rapporteurs for each round table is an essential step to guarantee the success of a world café. Preferentially an expert in the topic discussed would ensure that the discussion keeps a scientific rigor. The moderator must be a good communicator while respecting the allocated timing.

Time and human resources. Months of preparation can be needed for the organisation of a large-scale World Café, as demonstrated by the BANOS Mission Arenas. This aspect must be well assessed and considered when intending to organise a World Café with a group of 100 and more participants.

Mission relevance

The World Café method is particularly relevant in the context of the Mission Ocean and Waters. The Mission focuses on the co-creation of knowledge and aims to bring together diverse categories of stakeholders, following the penta-helix model. The World Café ensures an inclusive and participatory process, allowing all stakeholders to be represented and to have a voice in the co-creation process. Furthermore, Mission Ocean and Waters seeks to achieve specific objectives aligned with key EU policies. The World Café operates on a similar principle by inviting participants to provide ideas on how to address specific challenges or achieve clearly defined objectives. Organizing stakeholder assemblies in the Mission lighthouses using the World Café format can foster the co-creation of intermediary policies (e.g., strategies, roadmaps) that contribute to the achievement of the Mission's objectives. The roadmaps co-created through the Mission Arenas in the BlueMissionBANOS project

can be seen as an intermediary step to mobilize stakeholders within specific sub-regions, maximizing efforts toward achieving Objective 3 – a carbon-neutral and circular blue economy.

Key recommendations

- Consider the world café method when gathering stakeholders with the final objective to deliver a tangible result, such as a specific policy document (e.g., roadmap). Pre-identifying a clear objective is key to mobilise stakeholders in a world café
- Foster co-creation and ensure democratic participation. Each participant of a world café must be able to raise his/her voice. Various interactive tools can support the organisers in ensuring a democratic participatory process.
- Either used for big or smaller gatherings, a world café can turn a standard event into a much more participatory and dynamic process, boosting stakeholder engagement.
- Time and resource investment must be well considered as it requires significant preparation and pre-engagement process, often months in advance.
- Ensure strong moderation and rapporteur roles

4.2 Focus on role-playing game

The Atlantic and Arctic pilot stakeholder assembly combined gamification (or serious game) with a scenario workshop to address the challenge of engaging key stakeholders in marine conservation efforts, particularly in the Atlantic.¹² Needs assessments revealed a gap in involving the most affected groups in conservation measures such as restoration projects and Marine Protected Area (MPA) enlargement. This pilot assembly aimed to help Atlantic projects develop strategies to engage stakeholders effectively.

The scenario workshop was initially considered a suitable method for fostering dialogue among diverse stakeholder groups to identify effective solutions.¹³ In this participatory format, participants explore fictive scenarios—derived from real-life marine conservation challenges—by discussing possible responses to challenges such as restoration or MPA expansion.

The scenario workshop includes a preparatory phase where various scenarios are developed. These are not predictions, but imaginative situations designed to spark discussion. Participants work in small groups to analyse barriers, opportunities, and solutions, then convene in plenary to vote on the most effective approaches.

Why was a role-playing game format chosen? Given the pilot nature of the stakeholder assemblies, engaging local stakeholders directly proved difficult. Instead, inviting project partners with in-depth local knowledge to represent these stakeholders was a more practical solution. This led to the idea of introducing a role-playing game, based on hypothetical scenarios inspired by real Atlantic innovation projects.¹⁴ The game added a playful element to the scenario workshop, encouraging creative thinking and allowing participants to step outside their usual roles, consider trade-offs, and explore solutions applicable to real-world situations.

¹² Gamification definition from WaveLinks platform. <https://wavelinks.eu/explore/engagement-methods/333>

¹³ Scenario workshop definition from WaveLinks platform. <https://wavelinks.eu/explore/engagement-methods/342>

¹⁴ Role Play definition from WaveLinks platform. <https://wavelinks.eu/explore/engagement-methods/324>

The role-playing game was introduced as an alternative to a standard scenario workshop, aiming to spark innovative ideas while avoiding dealing with complex maritime spatial planning issues. The game engaged stakeholders in a dynamic and interactive way.

Role-Playing Game main advantages:

- Small group of stakeholders: A role-playing game is easier to implement with a small group of stakeholders, to ensure a good dynamic in the group and facilitate the moderation.
- Break-the-ice exercise: To boost the contribution of different groups of stakeholders that do not know each other yet, this game can serve as an excellent icebreaker before entering into formal discussions.
- Fit for long-term engagement perspectives: This game can be a playful manner to engage stakeholders that will have to collaborate in the long-term, such as at the start of a restoration project. Through the game, they can reflect on future achievements of their long-term collaboration.
- Empathy: By role-playing as a character from a different field, participants gain empathy for different perspectives and can better understand challenges from other stakeholders' points of view.
- Collaboration: The game encourages understanding of each participant's position, fostering collective problem-solving.
- Project Development: It allows project designers to refine their ideas, anticipate challenges, and better prepare for real-life conversations.
- Conflict Management: The simulation helps stakeholders navigate potentially difficult discussions with greater ease.

Methodology

The Role-playing game was designed based on two hypothetical scenarios, inspired by the oyster reefs restoration demo site from the [CLIMAREST](#) project, and the activities carried out within the project [OCEAN CITIZEN](#). These two innovation Atlantic lighthouse action projects provided a strong source of inspiration to elaborate the scenarios.

- Scenario 1. Inspired by CLIMAREST demo site 3 on oyster reefs restoration, this scenario features all the challenges faced by the main stakeholders of a fictional coastal city particularly impacted by the drastic reduction of the flat oyster populations. Exploring nature-based solutions, the scenario aims to identify all potential opportunities and trade-offs to develop a **collaborative restoration project**, involving all penta-helix stakeholders in this process.
- Scenario 2. Inspired by the activities carried out in the OCEAN CITIZEN project, this second scenario tackles the challenges related to the elaboration process of a management strategy for a **Marine Protected area**. Through this scenario, a public participation event is simulated, engaging characters representing local communities, scientists, policymakers, and industry representatives. Stakeholders are actively involved in shaping the plan, rather than just being informed or consulted. This will ensure that the final proposal for the MPA reflects a broad range of perspectives and promotes shared ownership of the planning process.

The goal in both scenarios is to create a shared vision that is grounded in empathy and mutual understanding among all stakeholders. To validate this collective vision, a voting system has been proposed as a tool for gauging agreement and ensuring that all perspectives are considered.

Given that the scenarios have already been defined, each with its distinct characters, they can either be used as-is or serve as a foundational framework for developing new scenarios.

Planning is crucial to implement a role-playing game in a stakeholder assembly, since developing the scenarios needs a strong understanding of the real ocean conservation challenges and specific needs of local stakeholders.

The role of moderator is an important element of the game, ensuring the discussions generate tangible solutions while guaranteeing a dynamic and playful environment for the participants. On this aspect, an expert should also participate to the game, to guarantee scientific accuracy.

During the Atlantic stakeholder assembly, the moderator notably suggested placing cards from the DIXIT board game on the floor, allowing participants to choose the card that best represents the character they will interpret.¹⁵ Feedback received concluded that it was as a relevant icebreaker before starting the game.

The role-playing game instructions and oyster reefs scenario, as well as the guidelines for the moderator are available in Annexes (Annex 7.3 and 7.4). These documents as well as the scenario can serve as a model for future role-playing game workshops in the context of the Mission Ocean and Waters (e.g. a restoration project or MPA expansion).

Mission relevance

The role-playing game is particularly well-suited for the social innovation component of the Mission due to its immersive, interactive, and engaging nature, which fosters collaboration, creativity, and problem-solving. By placing participants in different roles and contexts related to ocean conservation, resource management, or marine protection, the game encourages them to think critically, explore diverse perspectives, and experiment with new ideas in a safe, controlled environment. In the context of Mission Ocean and Waters, the game allows stakeholders, such as local communities, policy makers, scientists, and industry leaders, to step into each other's shoes, promoting empathy and mutual understanding.

Furthermore, the dynamic and adaptive nature of the role-play enables the simulation of real-world scenarios that require flexible thinking, negotiation, and decision-making. These experiences provide valuable insights into how different social, economic, and environmental factors can impact the success of ocean conservation efforts and offer a platform for testing potential solutions before they are implemented.

Key recommendations

- Involve a small group of stakeholders
- Strong pre-engagement activity. Developing a role-playing game based on hypothetical scenarios implies a good collaboration with stakeholders
- Pre-select a convenient moderator to ensure smooth, dynamic and relevant discussions, suited to the real-world situation
- Add a humoristic twist in the scenario to engage participants in a friendly way
- Make the best use of a role-playing game to:
 - Offer a dynamic moment in a standard workshop
 - Break the ice among the participants
 - Foster long term engagement among a small group of stakeholders

¹⁵ Roubira, J-L; Cardouat, M. DIXIT. Libellud, 2008. Board Game.

- Establish the foundations at the first stage of a project elaboration
- Manage conflictive situations

4.3 Relevant public consultation models

The Atlantic and Arctic pilot stakeholder assembly represented an opportunity to showcase relevant public consultation models with strong leveraging potential and applicability in the Mission Ocean and Waters context.

The “sea in debate” – An unprecedented large scale national consultation process on the future of the sea

From November 20, 2023, to April 26, 2024, a large-scale public debate on maritime planning took place in France, to discuss the future of the sea, the coastline, marine biodiversity, and offshore wind energy.

Entitled “the sea in debate”, this consultation process was organised at the national level to spark an overall debate jointly covering the topic of offshore wind energy planning and the update of the national strategy for the sea and the coastline and its Strategic Façade Planning Documents. It covered the four main French coastlines and allowed everyone to participate in a planning process on the future of the sea and offshore wind energy in 2024.

The “sea in debate” can be considered as a co-creation exercise to elaborate the national strategy for the sea and the coastline for the period of 2024 to 2030. This overarching policy notably supports the implementation in France of the [EU marine strategy framework directive \(MSFD\)](#) and the [maritime spatial planning directive \(MSP Directive\)](#).

Key aspects:

- ✓ It gathered more than 21 000 participants
- ✓ In total, more than 375 events were organised (online and in person) where stakeholders could share their views, ask questions and therefore be more connected to the sea
- ✓ More than 20 000 written contributions were received, which make this consultation a valuable exercise to shape a strategy that fit with the needs of the users of the sea.
- ✓ This six-month process also contributed to ocean literacy and to raise awareness of the challenges faced by our oceans and seas.
- ✓ An independent institution, the National Commission of Public Debate, managed the entire process to guarantee neutrality and impartiality in the conduct of the debate.

This best practice can serve as a relevant model to involve the public in the decision-making process of maritime policies and thus further connect citizens with our marine environment. Nevertheless, engaging ‘remote’ public, in the sense of non-specialist or people from areas particularly disconnected from the ocean appeared as particularly challenging, but can be made feasible through this large consultation process.

The ‘sea parliament’: A relevant sub-national consultation and engagement model to create a regional community of ‘blue’ stakeholders

Maritime regions play a key role in the development of the blue economy, particularly in French regions where they hold specific competencies related to the management of coastal zones, ports, and marine biodiversity preservation. Regional authorities act as facilitators, fostering dialogue among maritime stakeholders and leveraging their deep knowledge of local stakeholders to strengthen connections.

To enhance this dialogue, several French regions have established "sea parliaments", which bring together diverse maritime actors, including research institutions, decision-makers, the business sector, and civil society organizations.¹⁶ These parliaments provide a platform for stakeholders to exchange views and share their positions on sea-related issues, ensuring mutual understanding and informing the region's policy decisions.

The structure of these sea parliaments typically includes a main assembly with thematic committees, addressing specific maritime concerns, and a permanent bureau. They serve as advisory bodies, offering opinions and resolutions on maritime issues, which are then passed to the relevant authorities for further action.

For example, in the Atlantic region of Pays de la Loire, the Sea Parliament contributed to the development of the regional maritime strategy and supports its implementation. The second annual meeting of the sea parlement in 2024 notably focused on the outcomes of the “Sea in Debate” and provided valuable input for the preparation of the Atlantic Strategic Façade Planning Document.¹⁷

The flexible nature of these institutions allows for dynamic discussions and external input, with topics covered at the discretion of the region.

Sea parliaments follow the quadruple helix model, encouraging collaboration between academia, business, government, and civil society, creating a strong community of “blue” stakeholders. They also provide a vital link between local authorities and regional maritime stakeholders, helping identify needs, challenges, and potential solutions. As the region moves forward, the sea parliament offers an invaluable opportunity to connect, consult, and advise on maritime policies, reinforcing the region’s role in the sustainable management of ocean and coastal resources.

However, citizen participation remains a challenge, though this aspect is crucial to enhance the connection the public with the sea and achieve the Mission’s objectives.

¹⁶ Pays de la Loire Region ‘[assemblée régionale mer et littoral](#)’. Occitanie Region ‘[Le Parlement de la Mer](#)’

¹⁷ Pays de la Loire. Assemblée Régionale Mer et Littoral. Webpage : <https://www.paysdelaloire.fr/mon-conseil-regional/les-missions-regionales/energie-et-environnement/strategie-ambition-maritime-regionale/assemblee-regionale-mer-et-littoral>

4.4 Focus on the essential role of moderator(s)

In the different methods and practices presented, the role of moderator is indispensable to ensure constructive debates at the stakeholder assemblies.

In a consultation process, such as the “sea in debate” implemented in France, an independent moderator would guarantee transparency, neutrality and impartiality, and thus avoid biased discussions. The French National Commission for Public Debate is an independent national authority that guarantees the implementation of the right to access information and public participation in environmental matters.¹⁸ In this framework, such independent entities could be further mobilized to facilitate participatory and co-creation processes in the elaboration of environmental maritime policies.

When dealing with conflictive and complex situations between stakeholders, benefitting from the service of a professional moderator with a specific expertise on sea-related issues would be a key asset to have a strong understanding of the different perspectives and challenges faced by stakeholders, and help them coming to an agreement.

¹⁸ <https://www.debatpublic.fr/>

5 Conclusions

The PREP4BLUE pilot stakeholder assemblies provided a robust framework to help the CSAs engage their stakeholders and strengthen their involvement in the Mission. These assemblies not only facilitated connections but also enhanced the information available on the *WaveLinks* platform, refining the stakeholder engagement methods already tested in relevant projects.

One notable method was the World Café, which proved to be effective for both large and small events. Its key advantage lies in fostering productive brainstorming and ensuring that every participant's voice is heard. This approach can be particularly useful for large-scale co-creation processes, such as the development of policy documents like the Mission Arena Roadmap 2030, making it particularly relevant for policymakers.

The pilot assemblies also served as a testing ground for different engagement methods and event formats, shedding light on role-play. Given the diversity of stakeholders in the maritime sector, representing a wide array of social and economic activities, role play can be an effective tool for anticipating potential conflicts and challenges. Used early in the project phase, it helps reflect on potential issues and fosters understanding, for marine conservation and restoration measures. It also serves as a pedagogical tool to facilitate reflection on current conflicts, as well as an excellent icebreaker to build long-term stakeholder relationships.

These events highlighted the importance, and challenge, of ensuring that every voice is heard. They shared useful consultation frameworks, such as the French “Sea in Debate” and the regional “Sea Parliaments,” which demonstrated their effectiveness in fostering engagement. However, ensuring long-term involvement, particularly from non-specialists, citizens, and those not directly connected to marine issues, remains a challenge. Further testing of consultation methods across different lighthouses would help address these challenges and refine engagement strategies through trial and error.

Organizing stakeholder assemblies is a complex process that goes beyond typical event planning. It requires months of preparation for the elaboration of workshops, working papers, regular stakeholder interactions, and the selection of moderators. Depending on the scale of the assembly, it could represent an entire project work package. Financial considerations are also crucial to ensure success, often requiring the coordination of multiple funding sources and sponsorships.

In conclusion, while the pilot phase has provided valuable insights into effective stakeholder engagement methods, it is essential that the stakeholder assemblies be fully integrated into the projects, with increased resources and support for the lighthouses. Ensuring the impactful rollout of these assemblies will further drive engagement and accelerate progress toward achieving the objectives of Mission Ocean and Waters.

6 ANNEXES

6.1 Evaluation Matrix for stakeholder assemblies

1. Preliminary information on the pilot assembly

MAIN THEME of THE ASSEMBLY:

DATE:

PLACE:

2. Identification of stakeholder categories and their potential needs and interests

Please select below the categories of stakeholders that will participate in the assembly and identify for each one their potential needs and interests:

Governments and policy makers	YES	NO
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POTENTIAL NEEDS		
Need for adequate data for decision making	YES	NO
Need for funding	YES	NO
Need for legislative support	YES	NO
International cooperation	YES	NO
POTENTIAL INTERESTS		
Economic growth	YES	NO
Environmental conservation	YES	NO
Social well being	YES	NO

Private sector / Industry (i.e; energy, food, fishery, plastic reduction, blue tourism, restoration)	YES	NO
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If yes, please indicate below the different sectors involved in your CSA that would participate in the collaborative process of the pilot stakeholder assembly:

Sectors to be involved:

POTENTIAL NEEDS		
Clarity on regulations	YES	NO
Support for sustainable practices	YES	NO
Financial incentives or support	YES	NO
POTENTIAL INTERESTS		
Profitability and brand reputation	YES	NO

Sustainability	YES	NO
Market demand	YES	NO

Scientific research institutions/ Academia	YES	NO
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POTENTIAL NEEDS		
Funding for research	YES	NO
Open channels of communication with policymakers (and beyond)	YES	NO
Access to sites and data	YES	NO
POTENTIAL INTERESTS		
Scientific discovery	YES	NO
Conservation	YES	NO
Evidence-based policy making	YES	NO
Publication and recognition	YES	NO

Local communities	YES	NO
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POTENTIAL NEEDS		
Awareness and education	YES	NO
Employment opportunities	YES	NO
Assurance of well being and health	YES	NO
Sustainable resources	YES	NO
Representation	YES	NO
POTENTIAL INTERESTS		
Livelihood	YES	NO
Cultural preservation	YES	NO
Sustainable resources for future generations	YES	NO
Health	YES	NO

NGOs and environmental agencies	YES	NO
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POTENTIAL NEEDS		
Funding	YES	NO
Collaboration and partnerships	YES	NO
Access to sites and data	YES	NO
Advocacy support	YES	NO
POTENTIAL INTERESTS		
Environmental conservation	YES	NO
Community upliftment	YES	NO
Policy influence	YES	NO

Philanthropists and investors	YES	NO
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POTENTIAL NEEDS		
Clear impact metrics	YES	NO
Transparency	YES	NO
Efficient utilization of funds	YES	NO
POTENTIAL INTERESTS		
Return on investment	YES	NO
Philanthropic impact	YES	NO
Legacy planning	YES	NO
Environmental and social change	YES	NO

Media and influencers	YES	NO
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POTENTIAL NEEDS		
Access to information	YES	NO
Stories and updates	YES	NO
Collaboration for awareness campaigns	YES	NO
POTENTIAL INTERESTS		
Viewer engagement	YES	NO
Education	YES	NO
Storytelling	YES	NO
Reputation	YES	NO

3. Needs in terms of collaborative governance

As defined in the general stakeholder engagement guidelines, **collaborative governance** is a “strategic approach in public policy formation and execution that constructively involves individuals from the public sector, private sector, and civil society. This method is designed to unite a varied group of stakeholders, encompassing government bodies, local communities, industry players, NGOs, and academic institutions, to participate in a unified decision-making and policy implementation process (..). Collaborative governance is not just a framework for inclusive decision-making; it's a multifaceted approach that incorporates various strategies essential for addressing complex and interconnected challenges. These strategies include Integrated Management, Adaptive Management, Conflict Resolution, Co-Management, Policy Development and Implementation, Capacity Building and Education. “

According to the needs of your lighthouse in terms of stakeholder engagement, please identify the collaborative governance model(s) to be tested during the pilot stakeholder assembly:

<p>Integrated management <i>An integrated management in marine polices refers to a coordinated approach to managing marine resources and spaces that takes into account the complex interrelationships between different governances, ecosystems and human activities.</i> <i>Specific Integrated Management approaches within marine governance are:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ecosystem-based management - Marine Spatial Planning - Integrated Coastal Zone Management 	YES	NO
<p>Adaptive management <i>Adaptive management within the framework of joint governance in marine policy is a cyclical, knowledge-driven method that recognizes the intricacy and unpredictability of marine ecosystems. It emphasizes adaptability, modifying regulations and methodologies based on fresh scientific insights and shifts in environmental, social, or economic contexts. This strategy employs scientific surveillance and feedback loops to guide continuous policy refinement. Incorporating stakeholder engagement is crucial to this process, as it ensures that the perspectives and expertise of those directly affected by marine policies are considered.</i></p>	YES	NO
<p>Conflict resolution <i>Disputes are common among stakeholders with different interests and values. Collaborative governance includes mechanisms for conflict resolution, ensuring that different perspectives are respected, and compromises are sought.</i> <u>Types of conflicts in marine policies:</u> resources use conflicts, environmental conservation vs. economic development <u>Approaches to conflict resolution:</u> mediation and negotiation, consensus-building processes, arbitration <u>Challenges in conflict resolution:</u> power dynamics, differing values and interests, communication barriers, complex legal and regulatory frameworks</p>	YES	NO
<p>Co-management <i>Recognizes that the people who use and depend on these resources—fishermen, coastal communities, indigenous groups, tourism operators, and conservationists—can be powerful allies in conservation and management efforts. By actively engaging these stakeholders directly in the decision-making process, co-management seeks to leverage their local knowledge, vested interest, and investment in the health of the ecosystems, leading to more effective and sustainable marine policies. Such engagement is essential, as it ensures that those most impacted by management decisions have a voice and are more likely to support and adhere to the agreed-upon regulations.</i></p>	YES	NO
<p>Policy development and implementation <i>Problem identification</i> <i>Policy formulation</i> <i>Decision making</i> <i>Policy implementation</i> <i>Monitoring and evaluation</i> <i>Enforcement and compliance</i> <i>Review and adaptation</i></p>	YES	NO
<p>Capacity building and education <i>Enabling all participants to contribute effectively to the management of marine resources. They involve not only transferring knowledge and skills but also fostering a collaborative culture and empowering stakeholders to take ownership of marine conservation and sustainable use efforts. This ensures that all parties have the knowledge and skills necessary to participate effectively in management and decision-making processes.</i></p>	YES	NO

4. Outcome of the pilot stakeholder assembly

Based on the information collected above, please describe the specific outcome/deliverable you would like to obtain from the assembly (e.g. a roadmap, an agenda, guidelines, etc...).

Could you please describe as well how the deliverable of the assembly will be used afterwards (potential follow-up actions or activities)

Description of the deliverable / main outcome	
Follow-up actions	

5. Identification of the relevant method to engage stakeholders

Through the platform WaveLinks , an online tool developed as part of PREP4BLUE will help to choose the right method of engagement (e.g. dilemnas café, focus groups, hackathon, role play etc).

To facilitate the use of the online tool in order to identify the best suited methods of stakeholder engagement, we suggest filling-in the questions below, based on the filters of the tool.

- **Determination of the level of engagement**

Please select the most relevant level of engagement for the pilot assembly of your lighthouse

Inform	NO YES (please precise)
Inform/consult	NO YES (please precise)
Consult	NO YES (please precise)
Consult/involve	NO YES (please precise)
Involve	NO YES (please precise)
Involve/empower	NO YES (please precise)
empower	NO YES (please precise)
Collaborate	NO YES (please precise)

- **PARTICIPANTS**

Please select the average number of participants to participate in the assembly:

5-20	
5-50	
5-100	
10-50	
10-100	
10-1000	
20-100	

20-200	
50-1000	
Any	

- **DURATION**

Please select the average duration of the pilot stakeholder assembly, taking into consideration the limited budget for the organisation of the assembly (15K for each one):

1-14 days	
1-2 days	
1-3 days	
1-30 days	
1-365 days	
1-5 days	
1-7 days	
2-3 days	
3-5 days	
Ongoing	

6.2 Black Sea draft action plan

This draft action plan for the Black Sea is a separated section of the EcoDaLLi draft roadmap for the effective achievement of the Mission Ocean & Waters objectives in the Danube and Black Sea Lighthouse.

BLACK SEA

ACTION POINTS

- 01

Hydrogen Sulfide Removal and Energy Use - Develop and implement technologies to extract H₂S as a renewable H₂ source while simultaneously reducing toxicity in the sea.
- 02

Strengthening River Pollution Management - Enhance wastewater treatment in upstream areas, implement buffer zones, and promote NBS like wetlands to filter pollutants.
- 03

Coastal Habitat Protection and Restoration - Introduce strict laws to control urbanization, establish marine protected areas (MPAs), and implement beach nourishment programs.
- 04

Oil Spill Prevention and Rapid Response - Establish an early warning system for spills, mandate double-hull ships, and deploy microbial remediation technologies for cleanup.
- 05

Climate Adaptation Strategies - Promote coastal resilience projects, expand marine carbon sequestration, and implement ecosystem-based climate adaptation.
- 06

Invasive Species Control - Strengthen biosecurity measures in ports, improve ballast water treatment, and conduct regular ecosystem monitoring.
- 07

Sustainable Fisheries and Aquaculture Development - Enforce scientific fishing limits, develop sustainable aquaculture, and support eco-certifications for seafood.
- 08

Regional Policy and Governance Integration - Establish a Black Sea Environmental Council, align national policies with EU regulations, and promote transnational cooperation with the Danube countries through the EcoDaLLi Living Labs.

Funded by the European Union

6.3 Atlantic & Arctic Pilot assembly Role-playing game (instructions and scenario 1)

Objective of the game

The goal is to address result-oriented discussions leading to actionable solutions.

Materials

- Game scenario descriptions
- Stakeholder's characters cards and stickers
- Button stickers
- Voting cards (green, orange, red)
- Illustrative cards e.g. Dixit cards
- Digital screen or a Paper board

Game scenarios

Two scenarios are provided with printable documents as a summary of the context, detailed descriptions of characters and stickers for each participant to identify its role:

- The preparation of a **collaborative project for the restoration of oyster reefs** focusing on developing innovative solutions to combine the restoration project with the different activities of the fictional coastal area.
- A **Marine Protected Area Strategy** emphasizing on co-creating a management strategy from scratch

Role-Playing game methodology

- Each group will have between 5 and 10 people.
- It is advisable that chairs are arranged in a circle in a spacious room, ensuring visibility of all participants and the digital screen or paperboard.
- A moderator, a rapporteur and a timekeeper have to be assigned.
- Players have to choose a role to endorse from the different characters of the scenario. At least one representative of each group of the penta-helix must be played, which are
 - **Academia** (universities and research institutions)
 - **Industry** (business and private sector)
 - **Government** (public policy, governance)
 - **Civil society** (the public, NGOs non-focused on environmental aspects, media)
 - **The environment** (Ecologist NGOs and environmental agencies)

The game is structured as follows:

- scenario introduction,
- stakeholder expectation mapping,
- identification and ranking the stakes and needs
- co-creation of solution(s), and
- iterative voting.

Voting system

The voting system serves several important purposes:

- **To engage stakeholders' responsibility in clearly expressing their opinions:**
 - Green card: I fully agree
 - Orange card: I can accept it
 - Red card: I fully disagree
- **To encourage quieter stakeholders to express themselves**
- **To provide an opportunity to address objections (Red cards):**
 - To understand the reasons behind the blocking points
 - To bring up new ideas/proposals

When voting, each group has one vote. If there is more than one representative from any group, they must come to an agreement on how they will vote.

After the first vote, the proposal will be amended, and a new vote will take place.

Therefore, two voting sessions are scheduled during the role-playing game:

- After identifying a common base of stakes and needs
- At the end of the game

End of the game

After the second voting all participants must build an agreement on how to proceed, which serves to the rapporteur to explain the outcomes of that group.

Extended version

Play the joker card: The role-playing game can be enriched with the interruption of a new participant during the workshop:

- someone not invited who insists on joining the group
- someone invited but coming late during the workshop, etc.

Such a situation could occur in real life and become part of the game for training purposes.

This role-playing game can be adapted to any other co-creation scenario of your choice, in which case maybe some of the characters of this version can be used or ones developed, but the methodology will be fully applicable.

Enjoy the journey of co-creation and stakeholder empowerment!

PILOT STAKEHOLDER ASSEMBLY

OYSTER REEFS RESTORATION PROJECT

Description of the environment and context

SOME BACKGROUND INFORMATION ON THE NATIVE EUROPEAN OYSTER REEF

The flat oyster *Ostrea edulis* is a European native species that once covered vast areas in European coastal waters.

By the mid to late 1800s, flat oyster populations were largely damaged due to overfishing, often beyond recovery. More recently, the emergence of parasites combined with the proliferation of various predators and many additional, human-induced stressors have caused a dramatic decrease in the last remaining flat oyster populations. Today, this species has disappeared from many locations in Europe and is registered on the OSPAR14 list of threatened and/or declining species.

Although the species and its associated habitat have collapsed throughout Europe, it is not extinct. A growing number of restoration initiatives are under way to return European native oysters and thus the essential ecological functions and ecosystem services they supply, to European marine ecosystems in sufficiently significant densities.

How and why European oyster reefs can be considered as relevant nature based solution, which should thus be restored?

- They can reduce coastal erosion processes by dissipating wave energy through the formation of shallows, provide shelter and functional feeding, spawning and nursery grounds for organisms impacted by shifting environmental conditions, filter water and buffer biogeochemical cycles.
- Oyster beds and reefs could also play a key role in global climate regulation through carbon sequestration into underlying sediments.
- They are recognized as ecosystem engineers harbouring an important number of species which make these organisms key for the conservation of biodiversity and ecosystem functioning.

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PILOT STAKEHOLDER ASSEMBLY

OYSTER REEFS RESTORATION PROJECT

Description of the environment and context

CONTEXT OF THE SCENARIO

The Atlantic region of Kerlifornia in France hosts several of the remaining flat oyster populations of the country and appears as the best area to experiment an important restoration activity, to be largely replicated in Europe. Convinced by the recommendations from the Native Oyster Restoration Alliance (NORA), researchers from the University of Kerlifornia have the idea to build an important project in the famous Bay of Houatche to restore the oyster reefs, engaging all local stakeholders in this ambitious initiative!

However, such a project requires significant dialogue among all stakeholders, and their engagement can be hindered by the need to reassess various uses of maritime space to implement the new initiative. It might notably restrict the available space for aquaculture farms and surf activities.

Taking into consideration various socio-economic aspects and stakeholders' interest, several questions therefore remain to unlock potential obstacles for the creation and implementation of the project.

SOCIO-ECONOMIC ASPECTS

The Bay of Houatche faces significant challenges due to climate change, particularly rising sea levels. This picturesque bay is home to local fishing communities, aquaculture producers, and especially oyster farmers, who have relied on its resources for generations. Unfortunately, the decline of the European oyster reefs has impacted biodiversity and reduced fish populations and water quality. These reefs once played a crucial role in filtering seawater, benefiting both the oyster farms and aquaculture, but their loss has led to a decline in production.

Local fishermen now contend with the repercussions of past fishing practices that contributed to the degradation of this vital ecosystem. However, the recent release of a popular film featuring Kerlifornian surfers has sparked a surge in tourism in the Bay of Houatche, particularly for surfing activities. This has drawn a wealthy demographic from the bustling city of Losse-en-Geletz, many of whom are investing in second homes to enjoy the stunning views.

While this influx of affluent residents has led to rising property prices and some discontent among local inhabitants, it has also positively impacted the local economy, boosting the GDP of Kerlifornia by 10%. New bars, restaurants, hotels, and surf schools have opened in response to this increased interest. Additionally, some investors have approached the municipality of Houatche about a real estate project to accommodate the growing demand for tourist lodging. However, this initiative is currently on hold, as concerns mount over the potential for the bay to be underwater in the next 30 years....

PILOT STAKEHOLDER ASSEMBLY

OYSTER REEFS RESTORATION PROJECT - KEY FACTS

The main issues to be discussed in the role playing game

MEETING CONTEXT

Researchers from the University of Kerlifornia are very happy that on **Wednesday 20th of November**, they will have the opportunity to discuss this potential restoration project with local stakeholders, during a thematic meeting of the **Sea Parliament of Kerlifornia** entitled “nature based solutions for marine and coastal ecosystems restoration”.

KEY STAKEHOLDERS POSITION

Ahead of the meeting, different groups of stakeholders from the Bay of Houatche received the invitation with a short description of the restoration project, its ecological interests and potential consequences for the activities of the Bay:

- **Certain areas might be designated as off-limits to fishing, and the available space for aquaculture ponds could be reduced.** While these measures are essential for the long-term health of the ecosystem, they pose **challenges for local fishermen and aquaculture producers who depend on these resources** for their livelihoods.
- Nevertheless, **researchers are committed to involving local stakeholders in the restoration process.** In particular, they would like to closely **collaborate with oyster farmers in the design of monitoring of the restored oyster reefs.**
- However, the project might face **potential challenges related to increased tourism, particularly during the summer months** when visitor numbers peak. Scientists from the University of Kerlifornia measured a **high number of marine litter, chemicals from sunscreens, and other pollutants, such as cigarette butts, which might threaten the integrity of the newly restored oyster reefs.** Researchers have raised concerns with the city of Houatche about these issues, highlighting the **need for effective management strategies to protect the delicate ecosystem, and implement their oyster restoration project.**

KEY TOPICS TO BE DISCUSSED

As the project is currently at its development stage, the debate that will take place at the “Sea Parliament” will focus on three main aspects:

1. Legitimacy of the project owner :

Although proposed by Researchers from the University of Kerlifornia, the first question relies on the legitimacy of the project leader, **especially since one objective would be to upscale this restoration project in Kerlifornia and other areas.**

- Research institutes may be suited to lead experimental projects but not large-scale operational projects.
- Should the **management body of a local Marine Protected Area (MPA)** be responsible if the project is within an MPA and primarily aims to conserve the species?
- Should it be the **local authorities** if the ecosystem services benefit the entire community or align with their public interest missions (e.g., coastal protection, water quality management)?
- Should **oyster farmers** be responsible if the main goal is to maintain a broodstock for spat collection?
- Should **fishermen** be responsible if the objective is sustainable fishing after restoration?

2. Funding :

- **Who will be the main investor?**
- **What role is there for co-management between public and private sectors, public and associations, or other partnerships?**

3. Explore:

- Innovative solutions to combine the restoration project with the different activities happening in the Bay.

The main stakeholders from the Bay of Houatche and their perception of the restoration project

PHIL COTON
Mayor of the coastal city of Houatche

MAYOR OF THE COASTAL CITY OF HOUATCHE

Historically known for its high-quality seafood, Houatche suffered a blow to its reputation and fisheries due to the destruction of oyster reefs from overfishing. The recent tourism boom has revitalized the city and opened up new prospects for the younger generation. However, the rapid growth caught the municipality off guard, making it difficult to address the negative impacts effectively. Overwhelmed by daily challenges and struggling to envision how the city can leverage the restoration project to create a sustainable, environmentally friendly community, Houatche hopes the upcoming sea parliament meeting will help tackle these issues.

PAMELA SUMMER
Marine biologist

RESEARCHERS FROM THE UNIT OF MARINE SCIENCES OF THE UNIVERSITY OF KERLIFORNIA

They have worked on the restoration of marine and coastal environment and biodiversity for many years and are particularly excited about the project. They hope to collect more data and innovative solutions to protect this key species, which will nurture their research on nature based restoration measures for coastal climate change adaptation.

JASON MACBERNICK
Oyster farmer

OYSTER FARMERS

Oyster farmers have seen their activity declined and many of them have lost their job and reconverted in another sector. The remaining farmers pursue their work, strongly motivated by the desire to contribute to their local community. Particularly reluctant to the restoration project, they would perceive it in a positive way, only if it helps them to continue and expand their oyster farms in the bay of Houatche. If their activities has to be reduced for the implementation of the project, they hope to receive a financial compensation, since they feel that they have enough paid for the pollution of others...

BRIGITTE BREIZH-DOT
Representative of a Marine environmental NGO

MARINE ENVIRONMENTAL NGO

This NGO advocates for sustainable fishing practices, preserving marine habitats, and combating pollution. The organization often conducts research, engages in policy advocacy, and works with local communities to promote conservation efforts. It also raises awareness about the importance of healthy oceans for climate regulation and the livelihoods of coastal communities, aiming to foster a sustainable relationship between people and marine environments. However, the new president of the NGO, Brigitte Breizh-dot, views the restoration project as an excellent opportunity to finally ban fishing in the bay and significantly restrict water sports. Born and raised in Houatche, she has witnessed the transformation of her beloved city and the damaging effects of mass tourism on the bay's sensitive native oyster reefs. She favors strict bans over soft compromises.

KELLY WAVY
Representative of the Surfer Association of the Bay of Houatche

ASSOCIATION OF SURFERS AND KITE SURFERS OF THE BAY OF HOUATCHE

Most of the surfers are originally from Kerlifornia and have been surfing since they were born. They all dream of becoming the next king of the waves in Kerlifornia, running along the beach of the Bay of Houatche, just like David Arzeldoff in that famous movie. This is actually how they discovered this new surf spot, which is much more unspoiled than the artificial beach in the city of Losse-en-Geletz. With some able to telework, they fell in love with the bay so much that they even bought houses there, allowing them to surf after a long day of work. Despite their laid-back appearance, surfers are true nature lovers. They generally view the restoration project positively but are particularly worried that the bay might be closed to surfing, which wouldn't be "cool" for their fellow surfers.

6.4 Guidelines for moderators of role-playing games

These guidelines for the moderators have been prepared by the startup Synergie Littoral in the framework of the Atlantic pilot stakeholder assembly.

Maintain the right balance between instructions, active role-play, and following all steps. Pay particular attention to the following:

- Ensuring that all steps are treated as equally important
- Making sure all participants fully embody their roles
- Enforcing the rules of interaction, especially the principle of non-judgment, which can sometimes be challenging to maintain.

Keep an eye on timing

It is important to strike a proper balance between "we need time" and "we need to stay on schedule." This means that while a moderator may spend more time on one or more steps, they should compensate by adjusting the time allocated to other steps accordingly.

Always dedicate time for a debriefing

A moderator should dedicate a minimum of 45 min to debrief with all participants and to learn about the outcomes of the game.

Developing Active Listening

Active listening is a set of skills that can greatly enhance communication, relationships, and understanding among group members. Below is a non-exhaustive list of strategies for improving active listening:

- Give your full attention to the speaker
Eliminate distractions, such as phones, computers, or unrelated thoughts, to focus entirely on the person speaking.
- Maintain eye contact
Eye contact shows engagement and attentiveness.
- Demonstrate interest
Provide nonverbal feedback, such as nodding occasionally, and express emotions that align with the topic.
- Avoid interrupting
Allow the speaker to finish their thoughts before responding. Resist the urge to formulate a response while they are still speaking. Focus on listening to understand, not to reply.
- Practice patience
Allow for moments of silence if the speaker needs time to gather their thoughts.
- Develop empathy
Try to put yourself in the speaker's shoes to better understand their perspective.
- Remain neutral
Calm the internal voice of judgment or assumptions to fully absorb the message without bias.

Work on the posture of Moderator

The role of a moderator requires a combination of personal traits, professional skills, and a deep understanding of local dynamics. Key aspects include:

- **Maintaining neutrality**
The moderator must ensure that all stakeholders feel equally heard and respected. Neutrality means the moderator should have no direct personal, financial, or other interests connected to any of the stakeholders involved in the assembly.

- **Promoting inclusivity**
The moderator should be vigilant in ensuring that marginalized voices are heard and that no favoritism occurs. This requires a strong focus on individuals who may speak less or less loudly, with the moderator constantly reflecting: *How are the stakeholders who are not being heard enough?*
- **Encouraging open dialogue to build trust and uncover shared goals**
The moderator ensures that the group adheres to the group agreements. If rules are being violated by one or more stakeholders, the moderator should pause the conversation and help the group discuss what improvements are needed.
- **Facilitating discussions to resolve disputes and conflicts**
It is essential for the moderator to identify points of polarity and explore them at the appropriate time. The moderator should emphasize that polarity is a source of collective intelligence and can help uncover shared solutions.
- **Operating with integrity and transparency**
The moderator should always clearly explain the purpose of the workshop and the steps involved. It can be helpful to display the process steps visually in the room, as was done during the first test of the role-playing game in Bordeaux, so participants can easily follow the structure.

Share roles responsibilities

The facilitator should not be responsible for all processes

It must be very clear from the beginning that

- the whole group share the responsibility on the right timing needed for each step to adapt the speed to the group needs, the role of the facilitation is to adapt the timing listening to the feedback of the group
- volunteers among participants will be requested to play specific roles such as the rapporteur who can right down key content of the group discussions

=> sharing responsibility is key to involve participants actively in the process himself, which is key to improve engagement

Understand the importance of the Group Agreement!

Setting a group agreement provides a way to work together with a group of people at the service of a project's intentions serving the objectives of a meeting in the best conditions for the group.

We recommend the moderator to prepare in advance a set of 5 rules into a framework on the paperboard as follows and to complete them with the group:

- **Expressing Yourself in I**
 - o creating an authentic dialog with others
 - o taking responsibility for its words
- **Respecting confidentiality**
 - o the discussions will not be brought outside this circle
- **Suspend your "Voice of judgement"**
 - o adopting an open and caring attitude, without criticising or evaluating the words of others
- **Developing active Listening**
 - o listening with curiosity and empathy
 - o do not interrupt the other person's speech
- **Yes but -> And if**
 - o a positive communication technique that encourages openness and collaboration, rather than creating opposition
 - o saying "Yes, but..." can stop new ideas in their tracks, by directly highlighting obstacles or weaknesses

And to draw them on the paperboard !

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